

ASSESSMENT AND PREDICTORS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS IN HYPERTENSIVES ATTENDING A SECONDARY HEALTH CENTRE: RELATIONSHIP WITH PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND DIET QUALITY

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Abstract

The aim: this study aims to assess the prevalence of hyperglycaemia, the association between diet quality, physical exercise and blood glucose levels among hypertensives attending a secondary health centre in Nigeria. There is a paucity of data concerning these issues and the study would contribute positively to future management of the patients.

Methods: the study was a cross-sectional study of 354 hypertensives that was conducted at the State Hospital, Oyo, Nigeria. The systematic sampling technique was used to recruit patients, and the data were analysed using SPSS software version 23. Linear regression was done to determine the predictors of hyperglycaemia, and logistic regression was done to determine the predictors of diet quality.

Results: the mean age of the respondents was 52.60(SD±8.26) years. The prevalence of undiagnosed diabetes in this cohort was 19.60 %. The association of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) with High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) was negative, weak in strength and statistically significant (p -value = 0.034). For every 1 unit decrease in High Density Lipoprotein (HDL), there was a statistically significant increase in HbA1c by about 0.383 units (95 % C.I equals -0.737 to -0.029, p -value = 0.034). For every 1 unit increase in total Cholesterol, there was a significant increase in HbA1c by about 0.158 units (95 % CI equals 0.007 to 0.308, p -value = 0.04). Age group <45 years were about 2 times less likely to have good diet quality than those of 55 years and above (OR = 0.502; 95 % CI = 0.270 – 0.932, p -value = 0.029).

Conclusions: the study has assisted to characterise this population of hypertensives in terms of serum glucose levels. The prevalence of hyperglycaemia was high among these hypertensives. The predictors of hyperglycaemia were HDL and Cholesterol. Also, the predictor of good diet quality was the age of the respondents.

Keywords: diet, glucose, hypertensives, physical activity, predictors.

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1. Introduction

The increasing global prevalence of Diabetes mellitus (DM) has become a universal burden to human health negatively with accompanied mortalities. In 2019, DM was the ninth important cause of mortalities with a projected 1.5 million deaths [1]. The prevalence of DM continues to increase in Nigeria with associated complications and increasing burden on the health system [2]. Diabetes mellitus is an autoimmune disease which occurs because of lack of insulin or impaired response to insulin [3]. The diseases associated with obesity include hypertension, type 2 DM, and hyperlipidaemia. There are two types of diabetes mellitus. Type 1 DM occurs in about 10 % of patients with DM and type 2 which occurs in about 90 % of patients with DM. It was reported that obesity is a major

cause of type 2 DM. In comparing self-perception of weight and objective measurements of weights in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, Mogre et al reported prevalence of general obesity to be 32.0 % and abdominal obesity to be 58.0 % in a study conducted in Ghana. The sampling techniques were not explained, and most of the patients underestimated their weights. Weight management in the treatment of type 2 DM is very important to control the glucose levels among the patients [4].

In a study conducted in Lagos, Nigeria, high prevalence of Obesity was reported and elevated blood glucose, proteinuria and hypertension were associated with increased Body Mass Index [5]. The study was carried out in three of the 20 Local Governments of Lagos State as a Community study with a big sample size of 526 which made it more representative of the population. The prevalence of overweight and obesity was reported to be high in patients with type 2 DM in a Ugandan study. Although adequate sample size of 1275 was recruited, the study was conducted at a private Hospital making secondary generalisation difficult. Missing data was a big problem because case notes were used for data collection [6]. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of hyperglycaemia in adult hypertensives attending the State Hospital, Oyo, Nigeria. The study also aimed to evaluate the association between diet quality, physical exercise and blood glucose levels among the patients. There is a paucity of data concerning these issues. This study would help to characterise this population of hypertensives in terms of serum glucose levels and contribute positively to future management of the patients.

2. Materials and methods

A cross-sectional study of patients with hypertension was conducted from March 2021 to August 2021 at the medical out-patients clinic of the State Hospital Oyo, a secondary health care centre in Nigeria. The study involved 354 adults between 18 to 60 years (mean age of 52.60 ± 8.26) with an established diagnosis of hypertension and already on treatment for six months and follow up.

Bioethics

The approval of the Ethical Review Committee of the Ministry of Health, Oyo State, Ibadan, Nigeria was obtained. The Committee's reference number is AD 13/ 479/4023^B. Then, the Head of the Secondary Health Centre was informed about the study. Informed consents were obtained from eligible respondents before the administration of the questionnaires, examinations and investigations. Privacy and concealment of the respondents were guaranteed by the namelessness of the respondents.

Definition of hypertensive patients

Hypertensive patients were those with clinic systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mm Hg and diastolic ≥ 90 mm Hg diagnosed six months previously or patients on drugs for hypertension for at least six months [7].

Inclusion criteria included patients with clinic blood pressure of systolic ≥ 140 mm·Hg and diastolic ≥ 90 mm·Hg diagnosed six months previously or patients on drugs for hypertension for at least six months. Exclusion criteria included patients with severe hypertension, for instance clinic systolic blood pressure >180 mm Hg and diastolic blood pressure >110 mm·Hg who would need immediate evaluation, patient with emergencies, pregnant and lactating women.

Sample size was estimated using the formula [8]:

$$n = Z^2 pq,$$

where d^2 Quoting n – minimum sample size; Z^2 – the standard normal deviate, usually set at 1.96, which corresponds to the 95 % confidence level; p – the prevalence of hypertension to be 22.7 % for Nigeria [9]; $q = 1.0 - p$;

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.227)(1-0.227)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{(3.84)(0.226)}{(0.05)^2} = 270.$$

Considering 20 % non-response:

$$q = 1/1-fq \text{ is the adjustment factor } f = \text{non response rate, if } f = 20 \%, \\ q = 1/0.8 = 1.25, \\ n = 1.25 \times 270 = 337.5 = 338.$$

For this study, a minimum of 338 hypertensives were to be recruited. However, 354 patients were recruited to improve the power of the study.

Sampling techniques

The systematic sampling technique was used. About 80 hypertensives were seen per clinic which took place twice a week. Eight clinic days are run per month which means 640 patients would be seen per month. Three thousand and two hundred patients were expected to be seen in five months. The sampling interval was 9 (3,200/354). The first patient was recruited by Simple Random technique using computer-generated random numbers. Random numbers within the range of the number of registered patients with hypertension was generated using the random number function of Microsoft Excel 2016.

Precautionary measures during Covid-19 pandemic

Respondents were educated about Covid-19 pandemic. They were asked to use masks when coming to the clinic and wash their hands before and after consultations. Respondents were asked if they have had symptoms of Covid-19 positive patients or meet Covid-19 positive patients. Suspected cases of Covid-19 were counselled to go for the test. The principal investigator and the research assistants wore surgical masks, surgical gloves and ward coats to recruit patients. The laboratory scientists wore laboratory coat, surgical gloves, face shields, and surgical masks. Hand sanitisers with at least 60 % alcohol, tissue papers, trash baskets, cleaners and disinfectants were provided. The reasons for the assessments were explained to the respondents. The personal data of the respondents and the blood samples were taken.

Diet quality

The assessment of the diets of the patients Questionnaire (modified Rapid Eating Assessment for Participants – Shortened Version) was used to assess the diet quality. This is a validated 13-item questionnaire for a brief dietary assessment [10]. The Cronbach alpha is 0.86. It is used to assess the nutrient intake and assist in brief lifestyle counselling by a healthcare provider. The REAP-S questionnaire was scored by summing up the responses recorded for subjects. Responses of 'usually/often' received 1 point, 'sometimes' received 2 points, and 'rarely/never or does not apply to me' received 3 points. Possible scores range from 13 to 39 points with a higher score indicating a higher diet quality. Statistical analysis showed the mean score to be 30. Scores below 30 were regarded as low and scores of 30 and above were categorised as good diet quality.

Physical activity

The Global Physical Activity Questionnaire (GPAQ) was used to assess physical activity. It was developed by the WHO to assess the type, frequency, duration, and intensity of physical activity at work, transport and leisure time in a typical week. It has 16 items and is a validated instrument used in a previous study [11].

Scoring of Physical activity: Metabolic Equivalent (METs) are commonly used to assess physical activity. It is the ratio of work metabolic rate to resting metabolic rate. One MET is 1 kcal/kg/hour and is corresponding to the energy rate of sitting quietly. Walking was scored 4.0 METs, moderate physical activity was scored 4 METS and vigorous physical activity was scored 8 METS. Physical activity was categorised into high, moderate, and low. Physical activities less than 10minutes and more than 180 mintes were not counted. All activities were converted to minutes and multiplied by MET to get MET minutes. High level of Physical activity ≥ 1500 METs minutes a week, Moderate Physical activity was ≥ 600 METS minutes a week and Scoring less was Low Physical activity.

Glycated haemoglobin measurement

Principle of the procedure

The Bio-Rad D-10 Dual programme is designed for analytes separation by High Performance Liquid Chromatography. The samples were diluted on the D-10 and injected into the cartridge. The D-10 distributed an automated buffer gradient of increasing ion strength to the cartridge. Then the haemoglobins were divided based on their ionic exchanges with the cartridge materials. The divided haemoglobins then move through the flow cell of the filter photometer where variations in absorbance at 415nm were measured.

D-10 software did reductions of raw data collected from each analysis. Two-level calibrations were used for quantitation of the HbA₂/F/A_{1c} values. A sample report and a chromatogram

were generated for each sample. The A2, F and A1c points were shaded. The A1c area was estimated using an exponentially modified Gaussian algorithm that excluded the labile A_{1c} and carbamylated peak areas from the A1c peak area. The D-10 Double programme is for use only with the Bio-Rad D-10 Haemoglobin Testing programme.

Specimen preparation

Whole blood specimens were collected in vacuum collection tubes containing EDTA. Any materials of human origin were regarded as infectious and held using typical biosafety procedures. Specimens were kept at 2–8 °C but were allowed to reach room temperature (15–30 °C) before performance of the tests. The sample tubes were loaded into the D-10 sample rack and positioned in the D-10 ensuring that the sample barcodes were facing the direction of the back of the instrument. Special rack inserts for 12-, 13-, and 14-mm diameter tubes were used.

Diagnosis of Diabetes mellitus

Patients with fasting plasma glucose of ≥ 7.0 mmol/L, a 2-hour plasma glucose value in a 75 g oral glucose tolerance test of ≥ 11.1 mmol/L or a glycated haemoglobin (A1c) of ≥ 6.5 % [12].

Data analysis

The data were entered into the computer, cleaned, coded and analysed using SPSS software version 23. Frequency tables and diagrams in form of charts were used for relevant variables. χ^2 tests were used to test the significance of the association between categorical variables, and Correlation was used to assess the relationships between Continuous variables. Logistic regression and linear regressions were done to determine the predictors of diet quality and hyperglycaemia respectively. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance.

3. Results

Distribution of physical activity scores

Fig. 1 shows that about a third (30.8 %) of the respondents had vigorous physical activity and another third had moderate physical activity.

Fig. 1. Distribution of Physical activity scores

Distribution of diet quality scores

Fig. 2 shows distribution of diet quality scores. A little bit above average had good diet quality while a minority had poor diet quality.

Fig. 2. Distribution of diet quality scores

Distribution of HbA1c

Table 1 shows that one-fifth 71 (20.0 %) of the hypertensives were known patients with Type 2 diabetes mellitus. Twenty-four patients with type 2 DM had poor blood glucose control. Two

hundred and eighty-three patients had not been screened for DM. Fifty-five out of 283 (19.40 %) had glycated haemoglobin ≥ 6.5 %. Therefore, the prevalence of undiagnosed DM in this cohort was 19.40 % (55/283).

The prevalence of DM in this hypertensive cohort was number of known patients with DM (71) plus newly diagnosed number with DM (55) which would be 35.6 % (71+55)/354).

Table 1
Distribution of HbA1c

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Do you have diabetes mellitus?		
Yes	71	20.1
No	283	79.9
Undiagnosed DM		
<6.5	229	80.6
≥ 6.5	55	19.4
HbA1c(%)		
≤ 6.4	269	76.4
≥ 6.5	85	23.6

Relationship of HbA1c with selected variables

Table 2 shows the association of HbA1c with HDL which was negative, weak in strength and statistically significant (p -value = 0.034). For body mass index (BMI) and HbA1c, there was no association (p -value = 0.802).

Table 2
Relationship of HbA1c with selected variables

Variables	HbA1c
Physical activity	
Pearson correlation	-0.065
p -value	0.224
Age	
Pearson correlation	0.069
p -value	0.194
Diet quality	
Pearson correlation	-0.003
p -value	0.963
HDL	
Pearson correlation	-0.113
p -value	0.034*
LDL	
Pearson correlation	0.014
p -value	0.792
Total Cholesterol	
Pearson correlation	0.092
p -value	0.082

Note: Correlation is significant at 5 % level of significance (2-tailed)

Linear regression for HbA1c on significant variables

As shown in **Table 3**, for every 1 unit increase in HDL, there was a statistically significant decrease in HbA1c by about 0.383 units (95 % C.I equals -0.737 to -0.029, p -value = 0.034).

However, for every 1 unit increase in Cholesterol, there was a statistically significant increase in glycated haemoglobin by about 0.158 units (95 % C.I equals 0.007 to 0.308, p -value = 0.04).

Table 3

Linear regression for HbA1c on significant variables

ANOVA TABLE					
Model	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F	Significant
1 Regression	26.58	1	26.580	4.54	0.034*
Residual	2061.095	352	5.855		
Total	2087.67	353			
2 Regression	51.262	1	25.63	4.42	0.013*
Residual	2036.41	351			
Total	2087.67	353	5.802		

Linear regression for HbA1c on significant variables					
Variable	Regression coefficient(B)	Standard Error for B	95 % CI for B	p -value	T
Constant	6.68	0.324	6.04-7.31	0.0001	20.62
HDL	-0.383	0.180	-0.737 to -0.029	0.034*	-2.131
Constant	6.04	0.446	5.16-6.92	0.0001	13.55
HDL	-0.434	0.181	-0.789-0.078	0.017	-2.40
Total Cholesterol	0.158	0.076	0.007 to 0.308	0.040*	2.063

Note: Dependent variable: glycated haemoglobin; Predictors: HDL, total Cholesterol; *Significant at 5 % level of significance

Association of diet quality with selected variables

As shown in **Table 4**, majority (58.0 %) of the respondents who were females had good diet quality ($\chi^2 = 1.73$, p -value = 0.119). Majority (60.4 %) of those respondents ≥ 55 years had good diet quality compared with respondents who were 45–54 years of age ($\chi^2 = 4.89$, p -value = 0.02).

Table 4

Association of diet quality with selected variables

Variable	Diet quality		χ^2	p -value
	Poor	Good		
Sex				
Male	36 (50.7 %)	35 (49.3 %)		
Female	119 (42.0 %)	164 (58.0 %)	1.73	0.12
Age				
<45	30 (56.6 %)	23 (43.4 %)		
45–54	53 (44.5)	66 (55.5 %)		
≥ 55	72 (39.6 %)	110 (60.4 %)	4.89	0.02
Educational level				
No formal education	48 (44.0 %)	61 (56.0 %)		
Primary	26 (56.5 %)	20 (43.5 %)		
Secondary	23 (38.3 %)	37 (61.7 %)		
Tertiary	58 (41.7 %)	81 (58.3 %)	4.00	0.264

Association of physical activity with selected variables

As shown in **Table 5**, about a third (32.9 %) of the respondents who were females were doing moderate physical exercise compared with 21.10 % for males ($\chi^2 = 4.50$, p -value = 0.103). About two fifths (41.2 %) of those respondents ≥ 55 years had low physical activity compared with 34.5 % for respondents who were 45–54 years of age ($\chi^2 = 3.49$, p -value = 0.103).

Table 5
Association of physical activity with selected variables

Variable	Physical activity			χ^2	p-value
	Low	Moderate	High		
Sex					
Male	34 (47.9)	15 (21.1)	22 (31.0)	4.50	0.103
Female	103 (36.4)	93 (32.9)	87 (30.7)		
Age					
<45	21 (39.6 %)	16 (30.2 %)	16 (30.2 %)	3.49	0.483
45–54	41 (34.5 %)	34 (28.5 %)	44 (37.0 %)		
≥55	75 (41.2 %)	58 (31.9 %)	49 (26.9 %)		
Educational level					
No formal education	47 (43.1 %)	32 (29.4 %)	30 (27.5 %)	8.07	0.235
Primary	14 (30.4 %)	16 (34.8 %)	16 (34.8 %)		
Secondary	23 (38.3 %)	12 (20.0 %)	25 (41.7 %)		
Tertiary	53 (38.1 %)	48 (34.5 %)	38 (27.3 %)		

Logistic regression analysis of good diet quality on selected variables

Table 6 shows the logistic regression analysis of good diet quality on selected variables. After adjusting for other variables, the predictor of good diet quality was age. Age group <45 years were about 2 times less likely to have good diet quality than those of 55 years and above (OR = 0.502; 95 % CI = 0.270 – 0.932, p-value = 0.029).

Table 6
Logistic regression analysis of good diet quality on selected variables

Variable	Odd Ratio	Wald	95 % CI	p-value
Sex				
Male	1			
Female	2.49	7.09	1.272–4.868	0.210*
Age				
Age group <45	0.502			
Age group 45–54	0.815	4.76	0.270–0.932	0.029*
Age group ≥55	1	0.733	0.510–1.301	0.392

Note: *Significant at 5 % level of significance; Dependent variable: diet quality; Predictor: Age

4. Discussion

As body fat increases, fat accumulation in the pancreas could increase which has been linked with elevated blood glucose. The prevalence of DM in this population of hypertensives was about 35.6 %. About half of the respondents had good diet quality. Also, about a third of the respondents had vigorous physical activity, and another third had moderate physical activity. Physical inactivity tends to increase with age because most people become less active with age. The predictors of hyperglycaemia were HDL and total Cholesterol. Also, the predictor of good diet quality was the age of the respondents. The determinants of poor glycaemic control were poor knowledge of diabetes and the duration of diabetes mellitus according to the report of a study conducted in Warri, Nigeria [13]. However, the predictor of hyperglycaemia in a study conducted in India was waist hip ratio whereas the predictors of hyperglycaemia in this study were serum HDL and total cholesterol [14]. Gupta and colleagues in another Indian study also reported that the probability of developing Type 2 DM was twice or more in obese or overweight respondents compared with normal weight respondents [15].

About two-fifths of the hypertensive patients in this study had type 2 DM with a third of them having good blood glucose control. This showed that the prevalence of type 2 DM was higher in hypertensives compared with normal population and therefore hypertensives should be routinely screened for diabetes mellitus. Similarly, in a Ugandan study on patients with Type 2 DM, 28 % of

the patients were said to have controlled glycaemia which was close to the findings of this study [6]. The prevalence of undiagnosed diabetes mellitus in this cohort of patients was 19.4 % which also showed the significance of routine screening of hypertensives for DM. This contrasted with 7.1 % reported in a population of civil servants studied in Oyo state, Nigeria, by Olawuyi and colleague [16]. They also found that increasing blood glucose was associated with high blood pressure. Akinwusi and colleagues also found 7.3 % to have diabetes mellitus in another study in Osun state Nigeria [17]. The higher prevalence in this study might be because the population was made up of hypertensives.

The total dietary intake and quality of carbohydrate and fats were associated with abnormal serum glucose and serum lipid levels in a study conducted in Denmark [18]. Diet remains a key factor in the management of DM and one of the recommendations of the International diabetic federation. The prevalence of hypertension and diabetes among commercial drivers were 27.7 % and 3.4 % respectively according to a study carried out in Ibadan, Nigeria. It was also found that frequent fruit consumption was a predictor of diabetes mellitus [19]. There was no relationship between diet quality and serum level of glucose in this study. In another study to compare the lipid profiles of patients with obese type 2 diabetes and non-obese type 2 DM, serum levels of cholesterol, Triglyceride, LDL were elevated while HDL was reduced in obese patients. Although there was no significant change in total cholesterol, the study showed that obesity was associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus [20]. In an assessment of the relationship between glycaemic control and serum lipids among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, glycated haemoglobin had positive and significant association with total cholesterol, LDL and HDL. Dyslipidaemia is a predisposing factor to the development of diabetes mellitus [21]. This was like the findings of this study.

A tertiary hospital study in Nigeria among Nurses on the management of diabetes mellitus showed that educational intervention training could improve knowledge of the management of diabetes mellitus [22]. Protocols and guidelines were recommended to be placed in strategic positions in the hospitals to assist the nurses in the management of the patients. Patients were counselled during administration of questionnaires in this study. A cross-sectional study in Northern Nigeria showed 0.0 % prevalence of diabetes mellitus, although some respondents had impaired serum glucose levels. Glucose levels were found to be higher in males and the levels increased with age. However, a sample size of 78 would not allow secondary generalisation and that might also be responsible for 0.0 % prevalence [23]. Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is associated with maternal and neonatal complications and hence early detection and treatment can prevent associated complications. To determine the prevalence of GDM and associated factors, a study conducted in Ethiopia showed that family history of diabetes mellitus, obesity, physical inactivity, and poor dietary quality were associated with GDM. In addition, the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus was 12.8 % which was higher than the general population [24]. Some degrees of hyperglycaemia must have been induced by pregnancy. The incidence of post-partum glucose intolerance was high in patients with GDM and therefore post-partum screening for glucose intolerance is important for such patients to detect DM early according to a report by Muche and colleagues [25]. The prevalence of GDM was 14.9 % in a study conducted in Porthacourt, Nigeria. Increased serum glucose levels were associated with increasing age, weight, abdominal skinfold thickness and previous history of GDM. The independent predictors of GDM were abdominal skinfold thickness and previous history of GDM [26]. The report of a Nigerian study showed that severity, diabetes knowledge and health beliefs were associated with the management of diabetes mellitus [27]. Considering these factors in addition to other social factors will help to control sugar levels among patients with diabetes mellitus. A study conducted in Lagos showed poor nutritional knowledge and poor dietary pattern in contrast to the findings of this study which showed that a little above average of the respondents had good diet quality [28]. A tertiary hospital study in Nigeria showed high prevalence of prediabetes (22.3 %) among civil servants, and the predictors of prediabetes were sex, family history of diabetes and moderate intensity physical exercise. Regular screening for hyperglycaemia is recommended for civil servants to detect impaired glucose tolerance and treat DM early [29].

Implication of the study to research and clinical practice

This work showed that diet quality was better in the older age groups. Secondly, the predisposing factors to the development of hyperglycaemia were high density lipoproteins and total

cholesterol. Health care workers would need to update themselves on diet and nutrition to counsel their patients especially younger people on the consumption of high-quality diet to prevent non-communicable diseases including diabetes mellitus.

Study limitations. The study was a hospital based cross-sectional and the results obtained might not be a true reflection of what obtains in the community. However, the hospital serves a big population covering a very wide geographical area. Besides, causal relationships could not be established and hence there are needs for experimental studies to establish causal relationships.

Prospects for further research. The outcome of this research has opened doors for intervention studies especially the use of diets to influence blood sugar control. Randomised control trials will give a clearer picture of the impact of diets on blood glucose regulation.

5. Conclusions

The prevalence of diabetes mellitus in this population was about 35.6 %. About half of the respondents had good diet quality. Also, about a third of the respondents had vigorous physical activity, and another third had moderate physical activity. The predictors of hyperglycaemia were HDL and total Cholesterol. Also, the predictor of good diet quality was age of the patients. This study has assisted to characterise this population of hypertensives in terms of serum glucose anomalies, and this will be useful in their treatment and planning future care.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare there is no conflict of interests.

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